

ENGLISH IDIOMATIC PHRASEOLOGY IN THE WORKS OF FOREIGN LEXICOLOGISTS

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada xorijiy leksikologlarning nuqtai nazaridan kelib chiqqan holda ingliz idiomatik frazeologiyasi tahlili va talqini ko'rib chiqiladi. Turli yo'nalishdagi olimlar tomonidan taklif qilingan idiomalarning ta'riflari va tasniflari tahlil qilinadi, shu bilan birga umumiy qabul qilingan yagona yondashuv yo'qligi haqida ma'lumot berib o'tiladi. Maqolaning tadqiqot qismi xorijiy tilshunoslar J. Seidl & M. McMordie, L.P. Smith, Ch. Fernando & R. Flavell, F.R. Palmer, A.P. Cowie & R. Mackin, McCarthy, P.E. Howarth va R. Glaser kabi taniqli olimlarning ishlarini qamrab oladi. Maqolada idiomalarni aniqlashda noaniqlik, motivatsiya va semantik barqarorlik kabi asosiy tushunchalar ko'rib chiqiladi. Shuningdek, u idiomalarning frazeologiyaning boshqa birliklari, jumladan, maqollar, klişelar va frazeologik oborotlar farqlarining chuqur tahlili ko'rib chiqiladi. Bundan tashqari, maqolada idiomalarning stilistik salohiyati va ularning ilmiy-ommabop maqolalardan tortib, badiiy adabiyotgacha bo'lgan turli xil matnlardagi o'rni muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ingliz frazeologiyasi, idiomalar, xorijiy leksikologiya, semantik shaffoflik, motivatsiya, semantik barqarorlik, frazeologik birliklar, stilistik vazifa

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье исследуется английская идиоматическая фразеология с точки зрения зарубежных лексикологов. Анализируются определения и классификации идиом, предложенные учеными различных направлений, при этом подчеркивается отсутствие единого общепринятого подхода. Исследование охватывает работы таких выдающихся авторов, как Дж. Зайдль и М. Макморди, Л.П.Смит, Ч.Фернандо и Р. Флавелл, Ф.Р.Палмер, А.П. Коуи и Р. Маккин, М.Маккарти, П.Э. Ховард и Р. Глейзер. Статья рассматривает ключевые понятия, такие как непрозрачность, мотивированность и семантическая устойчивость, при определении идиом. Также она углубляется в различие между идиомами и другими фразеологическими единицами, включая

пословицы, клише и фразеологические обороты с предложением в качестве структуры. Кроме того, статья обсуждает стилистический потенциал идиом и их роль в различных типах текстов, начиная от научно-популярных статей и заканчивая художественной литературой.

Ключевые слова: Английская фразеология, идиомы, зарубежная лексикология, семантическая непрозрачность, мотивированность, семантическая устойчивость, фразеологические единицы, стилистическая функция.

ABSTRACT

This article explores English idiomatic phraseology through the lens of foreign lexicologists. It examines how scholars from various backgrounds define and categorize idioms, highlighting the lack of a universally accepted approach. The analysis covers prominent figures like J. Seidl & M. McMordie, L.P. Smith, Ch. Fernando & R. Flavell, F.R. Palmer, A.P. Cowie & R. Mackin, McCarthy, P.E. Howarth, and R. Glaser. The article explores key concepts such as opacity, motivation, and semantic stability in defining idioms. It also delves into the distinction between idioms and other phraseological units, including proverbs, cliches, and sentence idioms. Additionally, the article discusses the stylistic potential of idioms and their role in various text types, ranging from popular science articles to fiction.

Keywords: English phraseology, idioms, foreign lexicology, semantic opacity, motivation, semantic stability, phraseological units, stylistic function

Summarizing the information on idiomatic phraseology from domestic research and sources, it is advisable to turn to the works of foreign lexicologists, in which, as a rule, phraseology is not distinguished as a separate section of language science.

In the work of J. Seidl and W. McMordie "English Idioms and How to Use Them," first published in 1909 and reissued 43 times, an idiom is understood as: "a number of words which, taken together, mean something different from the individual words of the idiom when they stand alone" [9, p.4]. Seidl and McMordie provide various sources of idiomatic expressions: everyday life of Englishmen (e.g., "to be born with a silver spoon in one's mouth" | "to hit the nail on the head"); food or cooking ("to eat humble pie" | "to be in the soup"); agricultural life ("to go to seed" | "to lead someone up the garden path"); nautical and military life ("to be in the same

boat" | "to be in deep waters" | "to cross swords with someone" | "to fight a pitched battle"); the Bible ("to kill the fatted calf" | "to turn the other cheek" | "the apple of one's eye") [9, p.5].

This book also contains a classification of idiomatic units according to their equivalence to parts of speech (e.g., adjective + noun "cold feet"; verb + noun "to read between the lines"; idioms with prepositions and adverbs "by the skin of one's teeth" | "by all means," etc.) and according to their situational conditioning (Banking; Business; Buying and Selling; Health, Illness, Death; Holidays and Travel; Motoring; Politics and Government; Telephoning; Work and Industrial Relations) [182:202-216]. For example, in the subsection business, idioms such as "to make a go of a business" | "a sleeping partner (US a silent partner)" | "sharp practices" are provided. The authors also discuss comparisons (e.g., "as blind as a bat" | "to smoke like a chimney") and proverbs ("All is fair in love and war." | "Strike while the iron is hot.") [9, pp.233-247].

One of the early works translated into Russian is the book "English Phraseology" by Logan P. Smith, first published in 1925. The term "idiom" is used by the author "...to denote such language features, primarily phraseological units, which are speech anomalies, violating either the rules of grammar or the laws of logic" [10, p.10]. The work is characterized by simplicity and accessibility of presentation, but it does not represent significant theoretical importance for the present study, as the term "idiom" is not clearly defined enough, little attention is paid to the structural-semantic features of this type of units, common idioms are not distinguished from those that may have a specific color or limited sphere of application. The author strives to show the richness and diversity of English phraseology, to determine from which sources it penetrated into the common language, for example, from the language of sailors ("to set afloat"), fishermen ("to fish in troubled waters"), hunters ("to keep a dog and bark oneself"), natural phenomena ("once in a blue moon"). L.P. Smith delves into detail about idioms derived from literary sources (the Bible – "a fly in the ointment") and foreign sources (Greek history – "the Pyrrhic Victory").

Scholars Ch. Fernando and R. Flavell distinguish four types of word combinations based on the degree of motivation of their meanings: combinations with transparent structure, representing free combinations with literal meanings (e.g., "to break eggs"); semi-transparent phrases, whose meanings are mediated by metaphor (e.g., "to add fuel to fire"); phrases with semi-transparent structure, whose meanings

are not motivated by internal images (e.g., "to burn one's boats"); closed phrases, which are proper idioms (e.g., "to pull one's leg"). According to the authors, the criteria for identifying proper idioms are: 1) the meaning cannot be deduced from the meanings of individual components, 2) the presence of a literal homonymous equivalent in the language, 3) functioning as a single syntactic unit, 4) entrenchedness in the language [2, pp.18-48].

Another outstanding English philologist, F.R. Palmer, distinguishes proper idioms (idioms), partial idioms, and collocations. An idiom is "a sequence of words whose meaning cannot be predicted from the meanings of the words themselves" (e.g., "kick the bucket," "fly off the handle," "spill the beans," "red herring"), a semantically global unit but not a unified grammatical one. According to Palmer, the use of idioms in speech is associated with various grammatical and syntactic constraints. Speaking of grammatical constraints, the author points out idioms where the verb can be put in the past tense (e.g., "spill the beans" - "spilled the beans"), but changing the number of the noun (e.g., the idiom "kick the bucket") is impossible. An example of syntactic constraints is that some idioms can only occur in the active voice form (e.g., "the beans have been spilled" - possible; "the bucket is kicked" - incorrect). Palmer notes that some idioms are more frozen than others. Partial idioms refer to combinations of components with literal and figurative meanings (e.g., "make a bed," "turn one's back on"). Collocations are word combinations with various types of collocational relationships (e.g., the adjective "rancid" collocates with the nouns "butter" and "bacon"; "addled" - with "brains" and "eggs") [7, pp. 41, 94-99].

In the classification by A.P. Cowie and R. Mackin, which takes into account semantic and syntactic features, four types of units are presented: proper idioms (e.g., "fill the bill"/"fit the bill," "spill the beans"), semi-idioms (e.g., "foot the bill," "sink one's differences"), collocations (e.g., "take pains," "a matter of concern"), proverbs, and sayings (e.g., "out of sight, out of mind") [1, pp.10-25] The authors note that the meaning of proper idioms in general cannot be deduced from the meanings of individual components, as the special meaning is attached to the entire phrase. Semi-idioms have one component with a literal meaning and another with a figurative meaning (in the examples provided above, the first word has a figurative meaning). According to the authors, the degree of variability of individual components of idioms is largely unpredictable (The extent to which the form of an idiom can alter is largely unpredictable.) [10, p.20].

The renowned English lexicologist and lexicographer Michael McCarthy uses several terms to describe and categorize idioms: opaque idioms, in which the meaning of the whole cannot be deduced from the sum of the meanings of its components (e.g., "to kick the bucket"); semi-opaque idioms, which can be rephrased (e.g., "to pass the buck" and "to pass the responsibility"); transparent idioms, the understanding of which does not pose difficulties (e.g., "to see the light") [5, p.45]. In the work "From Corpus to Classroom," the term "idiom" is defined by McCarthy, A. O'Keeffe, and R. Carter as follows: "strings of more than one word whose syntactic, lexical, and phonological form is to a greater or lesser degree fixed and whose semantic and pragmatic functions are opaque and specialized, also to a greater or lesser degree" [6, p.80]. Idioms are relatively stable in their form, and a literal analysis does not allow for the determination of the unit's cumulative meaning. The authors adhere to a broad understanding of the concept of "idiom," including in this class phraseological units, proverbs, discourse patterns, and interjections (e.g., "there you go," "good god," "good grief") [6, p.85].

Continuing the review of the most well-known Western works, it is appropriate to focus on Peter Andrew Howarth's research "Phraseology in English Academic Writing," which includes both theoretical and practical parts. The author examines various types of word combinations, phraseological units, and proper idioms from the perspective of theories of different scientific schools, after which he analyzes written academic discourse (academic writing) using corpus data from students who are not native English speakers but are studying linguistics and phonetics at the University of Leeds, England. The analysis showed that idioms are absent from the texts, while phraseological units (e.g., "give rise to," "have something in mind," "make a point," "take something into consideration," "take place") constitute less than 1% [4, p.156].

P.A. Howarth lists the following characteristics of idioms: semantic opacity, the possibility of a literal interpretation of components, and structural immutability. He also distinguishes two types of units: proper idioms - pure idioms ("combinations that have a unitary meaning that cannot be derived from the meanings of the components. They permit almost no substitution and are unmotivated") and figurative (or motivated) idioms - figurative idioms ("combinations which have figurative meanings in terms of the whole. They may permit arbitrary synonymous substitution of one or more elements. They have a current literal interpretation and are clearly motivated") [4, pp.15- 47].

The term "motivation" is used in Russian linguistic tradition to denote the ability of the reader or listener to recognize the origin of an idiom, and this is what distinguishes figurative idioms from proper idioms. While figurative idioms possess motivation (e.g., it's easy to determine that the idiom "move the goalposts" is related to football), proper idioms (e.g., "shoot the breeze") are not motivated. The application of this criterion is not universally applicable, as English speakers may perceive the meaning of an idiom differently. Figurative idioms originate from metaphorical expressions that become fixed in language. Howarth writes that the diachronic factor plays an important role, as the initial motivation may become outdated, become less recognizable, and thus bring the polysemous unit closer to the proper idiom, for example, "bury the hatchet," "turn the tables on sb," "kill the fatted calf" [4, pp.23-24]. An important point of view shared by both British and domestic linguists is that there is no clear boundary between different classes of idioms and idiomatic combinations; rather, they represent a continuum covering both frequent and less frequent opaque idiomatic expressions.

Professor of Applied Linguistics at Leipzig University, Rosemary Glaser, defines a phraseological unit as a lexicalized two- or multi-lexemic commonly accepted combination of words that possesses relative syntactic and semantic stability, can be idiomatized, may have connotations, and fulfills an emphatic or intensifying function in the text. In dictionary entries, connotations are indicated by stylistic labels or style markers. The distinction is usually made between expressive and stylistic connotations, as well as register markers. The following designations belong to expressive connotations: derogatory, taboo, euphemistic, jocular/humorous; stylistic connotations include: colloquial/informal, slang, formal, literary, archaic, foreign; register markers denote a specific type of discourse, such as economics, judicial, medical, etc. [3, pp.128-129].

The main subtype of phraseological units is the idiom, which is a lexicalized, reproducible, commonly accepted combination of words that possesses relative syntactic and semantic stability, may have connotations, but whose meaning cannot be derived from the meanings of its components, for example, "to bark up the wrong tree" or "be born with a silver spoon in one's mouth" [3, pp.125-126]. Idiomatic units with a sentence structure (sentence-idioms) include proverbs ("Make hay while the sun shines" - all proverbs are idiomatic because their figurative meaning can relate to various situations, most of them have an instructive character); clichés ("We live and learn"); discourse patterns ("Come again? Mind the step"); slogans ("Value for

money"); commandments and maxims ("Thou shalt not kill"); quotations and winged words [3, p.127]. Phraseological units and idioms can undergo systemic variation and manifest their stylistic potential.

The emergence and distribution of different types of phraseological units depend on the type and genre of the text. R. Glaser examines the use of proper idioms and phraseological units in the following types of texts: popular science articles, as an example of language for specific purposes at the intersection with journalism; scientific monographs and research articles, as examples of professional communication; textbooks for adults (based on materials from the Open University of Britain); texts from journalism and commercial advertising; novels and other forms of fiction [2, pp.130-131]. The author's interest in various types of material and their stylistic properties is considered in this work from the standpoint of pragmatics and functioning. Style is understood as the choice of linguistic means made by each speaker or writer in accordance with the requirements of the communicative situation, depending on the following parameters: the personality and communicative intention of the author, the time and place of discourse, the discourse sphere.

To identify the stylistic role of a phraseological unit, various methods can be applied: the substitution test (i.e., replacing the phraseological unit with a less idiomatic analogue); the paraphrase test (if it is impossible to find an analogue, then it can be rephrased); the deletion test (which can be applied to check if it is possible to remove a given element from the text). Glaser also emphasizes the importance of understanding the stylistic features of the material under consideration. In popular science texts, writers use linguistic and stylistic means characteristic of the genre of journalism. In scientific texts, the individual style of the author plays a significant role, as they use stylistic devices to give greater significance to the subject of research. Textbooks predominantly use common idioms to facilitate the memorization and assimilation of material. Idioms and phraseological units are actively used in advertising texts, and headlines can also serve as slogans. In fiction prose, the author has a whole arsenal of various expressive means at their disposal, which are used, in particular, to characterize characters [3, pp.132-142].

In conclusion, Glaser writes that overall, the use of stylistic devices depends on the intention and personal preferences of the writer, so it does not always characterize a specific genre. Idioms add vividness and expressiveness to any type of text, and their stylistic potential is undeniable. Glaser even highlights a term such as

phraseostylistics, which combines systemic and communicative aspects of linguistic stylistic analysis.

Studying the terminology proposed by foreign authors allows us to conclude that there are no unified approaches and methods in describing the phraseology of modern English, indicating a broad definition of the boundaries of idiomatic phraseology composition. Authors' works are devoted to both the study of idioms in language and their functioning in speech.

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